

HERBAL MEDICINES IN MORDERN THERAPEUTICS

ABSTRACT :

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L.), a hardy perennial herb originating from the Mediterranean, is highly esteemed in the cosmetic industry for its multifaceted applications. Known for its historical use in traditional medicine, rosemary is recognized for its powerful bioactive compounds—carnosic acid, carnosol, and ursolic acid—that endow it with significant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. These qualities make rosemary a valuable ingredient in cosmetic formulations aimed at enhancing skin health, reducing signs of aging, and shielding the skin from environmental damage. The increasing global demand for both fresh and dried rosemary reflects its growing role in beauty and personal care products. Rosemary not only boosts the effectiveness and longevity of cosmetic products but also finds its place in a diverse array of formulations, from skincare and haircare to aromatherapy, thanks to its aromatic and therapeutic benefits. This review delves into the cosmetic potential of rosemary by examining its key bioactive constituents and their mechanisms of action. It highlights the latest research that supports rosemary's application in cosmetics, underscoring the herb's rising significance in the beauty industry and its potential to drive the development of innovative and effective cosmetic solutions.

INTRODUCTION ;

Since ancient times, plants have played a crucial role in cosmetics for human use. Although many modern cosmetic products have been developed, traditional herbal plants and natural products continue to hold significant value. Among these, rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L.), a prominent member of the Lamiaceae family, stands out as one of the most promising herbs. This fragrant plant not only delights the senses but also serves as a powerful ingredient in contemporary skincare and haircare [1]. Rosemary offers a natural approach to self-care, providing numerous benefits for the skin and scalp. It is known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antidepressant, and anxiolytic properties, which contribute to enhancing brain dopamine levels. In skincare, rosemary helps combat acne, unclog pores, detoxify the skin, and remove dirt and dead skin cells. It is also effective in soothing the signs of aging, smoothing wrinkles, healing eczema, increasing blood flow, and being used in aromatherapy. Additionally, rosemary is widely used in the treatment of diabetes mellitus, obesity, and dermatitis [2]. Its key active constituents, such as carnosic acid, carnosol, rosmarinic acid, and ursolic acid, offer therapeutic benefits that extend to relieving headaches, stomachaches, epilepsy, and rheumatic pain. Rosemary products, like rosemary hydrosol, are now used globally. This water-based product, obtained through steam distillation of rosemary leaves, can be applied directly to the skin or hair without dilution. However, rosemary oil may cause skin allergies or irritations due to certain chemical components, so caution is advised based on individual skin types. As awareness of the importance of herbs grows, the demand for rosemary has surged, leading to an increase in both quantity and prices [3]. History :Rosemary, a widely used herbal plant by ancient Egyptians, Romans and Greeks for decades for it's healing and cosmetic properties and it's use in traditional beauty practices. Greek scholars used Rosemary garlands during their examinations to improve their memory and to be alert. It was commercially found in USA and Europe for its antioxidant properties used in food industry [4]. Rosemary offers a natural approach to self-care, providing numerous benefits for the skin and scalp. Rosemary oil may cause skin allergies or irritations due to certain chemical components, so caution is advised based on individual skin types. As awareness of the importance of herbs grows, the demand for rosemary has surged, leading to an increase in both quantity and prices . It is also effective in soothing the signs of aging, smoothing wrinkles, healing eczema, increasing blood flow, and being used in aromatherapy.

Fig. 01

Kingdom – Plantae

Subkingdom – *Tracheobionta*

Superdivision – *Spermatophyta*

Division – *Magnoliophyta*

Class – *Maganoliopsida*

Subclass – *Asteridae*

Order – *Lamiales*

Family – *Lamiaceae*

Genus – *Rosmarinus* L.

Species – *Rosmarinus officinalis* L.

GROWTH AND PRODUCTION :

This herb thrives in temperatures ranging from 20-25°C and requires about 500mm of average annual rainfall. Its production involves several key steps: preparing seedlings, preparing the land, ploughing to remove weeds, transplanting, and harvesting—all of which affect the final product's quality. Subsequent processes include processing, packaging, transportation, and storage. For commercial use, essential parts of the plant—such as flowers, stems, leaf extracts, leaf oil, powder, and water—are extracted. The extraction process involves filtration, purification, solvent evaporation, drying, and sieving. Extraction from the leaves is performed using various solvents including ethanol, acetone, hexane, and carbon dioxide [5].

GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION:

Rosemary, native to the Mediterranean region, is cultivated in various countries including Algeria, Morocco, Serbia, Turkey, Russia, China, the Middle East, and to a lesser extent, India. It thrives in climates with temperatures between 20-25°C and is well-suited to Mediterranean environments. While it has been introduced to many parts of the world, it grows best in regions with a Mediterranean climate. Rosemary does not fare well in highly humid or very cold areas. Flowering typically occurs

from late December to April, with Spain being the primary commercial producer, followed by France, Italy, and Tunisia.

Ecology: Rosemary is a perennial chamaephyte, often found in garrigue and sparse pine forests, and is dominant in semi-arid Mediterranean bioclimatic zones [6].

COLLECTION AND CULTIVATION:

As a woody, evergreen shrub native to the Mediterranean, rosemary is cultivated globally both for ornamental purposes and commercial use. Cultivation requires land that is weed-free and well-prepared; the soil should be ploughed two or three times to create favorable conditions for seedlings. Rosemary prefers sandy loam soil and is not suited to areas with high clay content or waterlogged conditions. For essential oil extraction, 100 grams of dried leaves are subjected to hydro-distillation using a Clevenger-type apparatus for 3 hours. The essential oil is then recovered and stored in sealed vials at 4°C, protected from light, until analysis [8].

PHYTOCONSTITUENT :

Rosemary is rich in various phytoconstituents, making it valuable for skincare and haircare products. Key chemical constituents in rosemary extract include flavonoids, monoterpenoids, phenolic acids, and diterpenoids. Flavonoids in rosemary include pelargonidin-3,5-diglucoside, cyanidin-3,5-diglucoside, and kaempferol. The herb contains about 14.9% phenolic acids, notably rosmarinic and caffeic acids [9]. Diterpenoids, which contribute to rosemary's distinctive pungent and slightly astringent aroma, include carnosic acid, methyl carnosate, 12-methoxycarnosic acid, and epi- and isorosmanol [10].

fig 2:phytoconstituents

COSMETIC USES:

Rosemary oil, extracted from the leaves and blossoms of the plant, is widely utilized in aromatherapy and skincare products due to its refreshing aroma and therapeutic properties. Its diverse benefits for skin and hair make it a popular ingredient in numerous cosmetic formulations [11]. The oil's

effectiveness is largely attributed to its bioactive compounds, including carnosic acid, carnosol, rosmarinic acid, and ursolic acid. These compounds work synergistically to address various skin and hair concerns through their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant properties.

Carnosic acid and carnosol help reduce inflammation and control excess sebum production, while rosmarinic acid and ursolic acid inhibit acne-causing bacteria, thus soothing inflamed skin, unclogging pores, and reducing acne lesions. The antioxidant properties of these compounds neutralize free radicals, protecting the skin from oxidative stress and improving elasticity and firmness. This action reduces the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles, contributing to a more youthful complexion. Additionally, carnosic acid and rosmarinic acid alleviate redness and itching by calming inflammation, while ursolic acid promotes skin healing, which can be beneficial for conditions like eczema and dermatitis [12]. Rosemary oil also enhances skin detoxification by stimulating blood circulation and aiding in toxin removal, leading to a cleaner, more radiant complexion. Its antimicrobial properties support a healthy scalp environment by reducing dandruff and preventing flakiness. Furthermore, carnosic acid and ursolic acid improve blood circulation to the scalp, enhancing nutrient delivery to hair follicles, which promotes stronger and healthier hair growth and reduces thinning [13].

SKIN BENEFITS

- **Anti-Acne Properties:** Rosemary oil's antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects help in treating acne by reducing excess oil production, unclogging pores, and eliminating acne-causing bacteria [14].
- **Anti-Aging Effects:** Its antioxidant properties combat free radicals, which are a primary cause of skin aging. Regular use can minimize fine lines and wrinkles while enhancing skin elasticity and firmness.
- **Eczema and Dermatitis Relief:** Rosemary oil's soothing and anti-inflammatory properties are effective in treating eczema and dermatitis, calming irritated skin, reducing redness, and promoting healing.
- **Skin Detoxification:** By stimulating circulation and promoting toxin elimination, rosemary oil revitalizes the skin, giving it a healthy and radiant appearance [15].

Hair Benefits:

- **Scalp Health:** Rosemary oil promotes a healthy scalp by soothing dryness and itchiness, reducing dandruff, and preventing flakiness. Its antifungal and antibacterial properties help maintain a clean scalp environment.
- **Hair Growth Stimulation:** The oil stimulates blood circulation in the scalp, encouraging stronger and healthier hair growth. Regular use can result in thicker, fuller hair over time.
- **Hair Strengthening:** Rich in nutrients and antioxidants, rosemary oil strengthens hair strands, reduces breakage and split ends, and adds natural shine.
- **Prevention of Premature Graying:** Traditionally used to prevent premature graying, rosemary oil's antioxidant properties help combat oxidative stress that can lead to early hair graying.

Aromatherapy and Wellness:

- **Stress Relief:** In aromatherapy, rosemary oil is valued for its calming effects. Inhaling the oil can reduce anxiety, uplift mood, and improve mental clarity.

- **Improved Circulation:** When massaged onto the skin, rosemary oil can enhance blood circulation, which supports overall skin and hair health [17].

TOXIC EFFECTS

Ingestion -Consuming excessive amounts of rosemary may lead to severe side effects like vomiting, spasms, coma and pulmonary edema. It can also result in kidney damage, which can manifest as frequent urination, excessive thirst, dehydration, weight loss and depression. In extreme situations, symptoms of uremia, including mouth sores and neurological issues may occur. Furthermore, rosemary can provoke seizures in individuals with a history of seizures or epilepsy. Pregnant and breastfeeding women should avoid rosemary supplements as they might induce miscarriage. Individuals with high blood pressure, ulcers, Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis should also refrain from using rosemary [18]. Topical application - Applying concentrated rosemary oil to the skin can lead to irritation, redness or a burning sensation, particularly in those with sensitive skin. It may also trigger allergic reactions, including skin irritation, itching or respiratory problems. Inhalation- Using rosemary for aromatherapy is generally considered safe, though some individuals may experience allergic reactions[19].

MORDEEN THERAPEUTICS :

Recently, scientific interest has increasingly focused on the therapeutic properties of various rosemary extracts. Key constituents such as carnosic acid, carnosol, and rosmarinic acid are particularly notable. These compounds offer a range of medicinal benefits, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, neuroprotective, antidepressant, and memory-enhancing effects.

Antidepressant Activity: The antidepressant effects of rosemary are primarily associated with hydroalcoholic extracts of its leaves and stems. Additionally, hexane, ethanolic extracts, and certain isolated compounds from rosemary have demonstrated antidepressant properties. Essential oils containing carnosol, ursolic acid, and other compounds also show antidepressant activity.

Anti-Inflammatory Effects: Carnosic acid, a major compound in rosemary, exhibits significant anti-inflammatory activity. In Alzheimer's disease, carnosic acid is converted into an active form that influences oxidative stress and activates transcriptional pathways, leading to anti-inflammatory effects.

Neuroprotective and Cognitive Benefits: Rosemary extracts, particularly those with high carnosic acid content, may help improve working and spatial memory deficits and reduce neuronal degeneration. They also show potential in decreasing seizures and neuronal damage by mitigating the overactivity of glutamate receptors, which is linked to neurodegeneration.

Antinociceptive Activity: Rosemary essential oil has demonstrated significant antinociceptive effects in tests such as the acidic acid-induced abdominal writhing test. It also enhances the absorption and efficacy of topical analgesics like diclofenac gel.

Diabetes Management: Rosemary extracts have shown promise in improving hyperglycemia and alleviating hyperalgesia (increased sensitivity to pain). Its phenolic compounds offer beneficial effects against diabetes and associated complications, including neuronal tissue damage, neuropathy, and retinopathy[20].

Memory Boosting: Studies indicate that rosemary extract can reduce levels of oxidative stress markers like 4-hydroxynonenal and protein carbonyls in brain tissue, which is associated with improved cognitive function. Extracts from dried rosemary leaves have shown potential in enhancing cognitive abilities. Overall, rosemary and its extracts offer a wide range of therapeutic benefits, and ongoing research continues to explore and validate these effects.

Figure 3;Rosmaric acid

MARKETED FORMULATION :

Sr	Type	Brand name	Company name	Dose	Price
1	Hair oil	Amala hair oil	Dabur	Use 2-3 time in week	373
2	Hair spray	Metaverse hair spray	Metaverse herbal private limited	Use once or twice a day	799
3	Face serum	Rosemary essential oil	Virgo international	2-3drops 2 times a day	280
4	Hair shampoo	Mamaearth Rosemary shampoo	Honasa consumer limited	Once or twice a week	503
5	Face wash	Rosemary face wash	Shalazio	2-3 times a day	549

Table:1 Marketed formulation of rosemary oil

HOMEMADE REMEDIES

Rosemary is highly medicinal plant , the parts used are roots , barks, leaves and ripe fruits. Roots and bark- These are used for healing intermittent fever ,thirst and body pain .Leaves -These are used for treating ophthalmia ,deafness ,indigestion ,piles and jaundice .Leaf juice is used in curing cataracts and fever . It is highly used as antioxidant and cosmetic . It helps to protects skin and hair from free radical and environmental stressors that can cause the visible signs of premature skin ageing and damaged hair .This is useful ingredient in cosmetics industry, formulated for sensitive , irritated skin or scalp[21]. It contains natural antimicrobial and antifungal properties .This makes it useful ingredient in facial cleansers or shampoos for those who are prone to breakout or scalp issues(.It is also used in shower and bath preparations and aromatherapy product like massage oils or room sprays. It fights acne , thus has antiseptic qualities too [22]. This help to kill the acne, causing bacterial infection and is used for solution preparation to cure popped pimple wound that may get re-infected by acne germs. It heals skin conditions such as eczema . It is useful to cure stretch mark and acts effectively on all skin type[23] .It is also considered to be a non toxic stretch mark massage oil [24] .

CONCLUSION:

Rosemary oil stands out as a versatile and potent natural ingredient in the cosmetic industry offering a wide range of benefits for both skin and hair. Its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties make it an effective solution for common skin issues such as acne, aging and inflammatory conditions like eczema .

Additionally rosemary oil's ability to promote scalp health, stimulate hair growth and strengthen hair strands underscores its value in haircare. Beyond its topical uses rosemary oil's role in aromatherapy highlights its holistic approach to wellness offering stress relief and improved circulation. As interest in natural and herbal cosmetics continues to grow rosemary oil remains a key component in the development of effective and innovative beauty products. However, due to its potency careful application is essential to avoid potential skin irritation. Overall rosemary oil's diverse benefits and natural origin make it a valuable addition to any skincare and haircare products.

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